

Optimization of the Compressive Strength Characteristics of Four-Component Concrete Mixes Made with Unwashed Local Gravel using Second-Degree Polynomial

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Abstract:- Being able to predict the strength characteristics of concrete can be of great advantage in the design and construction of structural members. This research work set out to develop a model for the compressive strength characteristics of concrete made with unwashed local gravel based on Prof. Osadebe’s optimization theory or second-degree polynomial. The unwashed aggregate was from Abagana and the river sand from Amansea, both in Anambra State. These aggregates were tested for their physical and mechanical properties based on BS 812: Part 2:1975 and BS 812: Part 3: 1975. Sixty concrete cubes of dimensions 150 mm X 150mm X 150mm —three cubes for each experimental point were made, cured and tested according to BS 1881:1983. The model equation developed was $\hat{Y} = -2006.1Z_1 + 1401.02Z_2 - 90.3Z_3 - 105.47Z_4 + 91.79Z_1Z_2 - 9086Z_1Z_3 + 3268.26Z_1Z_4 + 7888.31Z_2Z_3 - 1636.57Z_2Z_4 + 427.5Z_3Z_4$. The student’s t-test and the Fisher’s test were used to prove the adequacy of the model. The strengths predicted by the model were in complete agreement with the experimentally obtained values and the null hypothesis was satisfied.

Keywords:- Characteristics, Compressive, Concrete, Component, Local Gravel, Mixes, Optimization, Polynomial, Second-Degree, Strength, Unwashed.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ Osadebe’s Concrete Optimisation Theory

Concrete is a four-component material of mixing water, cement, fine and coarse aggregates. These ingredients are mixed in rational proportions to achieve desired strength of the hardened concrete [1]. Let us consider an arbitrary amount, S, of a given concrete mixture and S_i, the portion of the ith component of the four constituent materials of the concrete where i = 1,2,3,4, then in keeping with the principle of absolute volume or mass [2]:

$$\sum S_i = S \text{-----1}$$

Dividing through by S and substituting Z_i for S_i/S gives:

$$\sum Z_i = 1 \text{-----2}$$

Then, the compressive strength of concrete can be expressed as equation 3:

$$Y = f(Z_i) \text{-----3}$$

Using Taylor’s theorem and the assumption that Y is continuous, equation 3 becomes:

$$f(Z) = f(Z^{(0)}) + \sum \partial f / \partial Z_i(Z^{(0)})(Z_i - Z_i^{(0)}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum \partial^2 f(Z^{(0)}) / \partial Z_i \partial Z_j(Z^{(0)})(Z_i - Z_i^{(0)})(Z_j - Z_j^{(0)}) + \frac{1}{2} \sum \partial^2 f(Z^{(0)}) / \partial Z_i^2 \partial Z_j^2 (Z_i - Z_i^{(0)})^2 + \text{-----4}$$

(1 ≤ i ≤ 4, 1 ≤ i ≤ 3, 1 ≤ i ≤ 4, 1 ≤ i ≤ 4) respectively and Z⁽⁰⁾ = 0.

If b₀ = f(0), b_i = ∂f(0)/∂Z_i, b_{ij} = ∂²f(0)/∂Z_i∂Z_j and b_{ii} = ∂²f(0)/∂Z_i², then eqn. 4 can be written as follows:

$$f(Z) = b_0 + \sum b_i Z_i + \sum b_{ij} Z_i Z_j + \sum b_{ii} Z_i^2 + \text{-----5}$$

Multiplying eqn.2 by b₀ we have

$$b_0 Z_i = b_0 \text{-----6}$$

Also, multiplying eqn. 2 by Z₁, Z₂, Z₃ and Z₄ in succession, making Z₁², Z₂², Z₃² and Z₄² the subject of the formula, substituting into eqn. 5 and factorizing gives:

$$Y = \sum \beta_i Z_i + \sum \beta_{ij} Z_i Z_j \text{-----7}$$

(1 ≤ i ≤ j ≤ 4)

Where β_i = b₀ + b_i + b_{ii} and β_{ij} = b_{ij} - b_{ii} - b_{jj} (i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4)

19	0.855	1	2	3	0.125	0.146	0.292	0.438
20	0.8595	1	2.75	4	0.100	0.116	0.319	0.465

LEGEND: S₁= water/cement ratio; S₂=Cement; S₃=Fine aggregate; S₄=Coarse aggregate, Z_i = S_i/S

Table 2 Z^T Matrix

Z ₁	Z ₂	Z ₃	Z ₄	Z ₁ Z ₂	Z ₁ Z ₃	Z ₁ Z ₄	Z ₂ Z ₃	Z ₂ Z ₄	Z ₃ Z ₄
0.105	0.119	0.298	0.477	0.013	0.031	0.050	0.036	0.057	0.142
0.109	0.127	0.254	0.509	0.014	0.028	0.056	0.032	0.065	0.129
0.116	0.136	0.272	0.476	0.016	0.032	0.055	0.037	0.065	0.129
0.125	0.146	0.292	0.437	0.018	0.037	0.055	0.042	0.064	0.127
0.109	0.127	0.318	0.446	0.014	0.035	0.049	0.041	0.057	0.142
0.098	0.113	0.338	0.451	0.011	0.033	0.044	0.038	0.051	0.153
0.093	0.107	0.320	0.480	0.010	0.030	0.045	0.034	0.051	0.154
0.135	0.157	0.236	0.472	0.021	0.032	0.064	0.037	0.074	0.111
0.107	0.125	0.343	0.424	0.013	0.037	0.046	0.043	0.053	0.146
0.107	0.123	0.246	0.524	0.013	0.026	0.056	0.030	0.065	0.129

Table 3 Responses of the Mix Ratios

S/NO	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	AVERAGE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH[N/mm ²]
1	0.88	1	2.5	4	13.2
2	0.86	1	2	4	13.8
3	0.855	1	2	3.5	14.6
4	0.86	1	2	3	15.3
5	0.855	1	2.5	3.5	14.5
6	0.865	1	3	4	10.3
7	0.87	1	3	4.5	9.8
8	0.86	1	1.5	3	16.6
9	0.86	1	2.75	3.4	14.9
10	0.865	1	2	4.25	13.5

LEGEND: S₁= water/cement ratio; S₂=Cement; S₃=Fine aggregate; S₄=Coarse aggregate

➤ *Testing the Fit of the Quadratic Polynomials*

The polynomial regression equation developed was tested to see if the model agreed with the actual experimental results. The null hypothesis was denoted by H₀ and the alternative by H₁.

Fig 1 Grading Curve for the Fine Aggregate

Fig 2 Grading Curve for the Local Gravel

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Physical and Mechanical Properties of Aggregates*

Sieve analyses of both the fine and coarse aggregates were performed and the grading curves shown in figures 1 and 2. These grading curves showed the particle size distribution of the aggregates. The maximum aggregate size for the unwashed gravel was 53 mm and 2mm for the fine sand. The local gravel had water absorption of 4.55%, moisture content of 53.25 %, apparent specific gravity of 1.88, Los Angeles abrasion value of 60% and bulk density of 1302.7 kg/m³.

➤ *The Regression Equation for the Compressive Strength Tests Results*

Solution of eqn.9, given Z^T values of table 2 and the responses (average compressive strengths) in table 3 gave the values of the unknown coefficients of the regression equation (eqn.7) as follows:

$\beta_1 = -2006.1, \beta_2 = 1401.02, \beta_3 = -90.3, \beta_4 = -105.47,$
 $\beta_{12} = 91.79, \beta_{13} = -9086, \beta_{14} = 3268.26, \beta_{23} = 7888.31, \beta_{24} = -$
 $1636.57, \beta_{34} = 427.5.$ Thus, from eqn.7, the model equation based on Osadebe’s second-degree polynomial was given by:

$$\hat{Y} = -2006.1Z_1 + 1401.02Z_2 - 90.3Z_3 - 105.47Z_4 + 91.79Z_1Z_2 - 9086Z_1Z_3 + 3268.26Z_1Z_4 + 7888.31Z_2Z_3 - 1636.57Z_2Z_4 + 427.5Z_3Z_4.$$

➤ *Fit of the Polynomial*

Selected mix ratios and component’s fraction based on Osadebe’s second degree polynomial was shown in table 1. The polynomial regression equation developed i.e., $\hat{Y} = -2006.1Z_1 + 1401.02Z_2 - 90.3Z_3 - 105.47Z_4 + 91.79Z_1Z_2 - 9086Z_1Z_3 + 3268.26Z_1Z_4 + 7888.31Z_2Z_3 - 1636.57Z_2Z_4 + 427.5Z_3Z_4,$ was tested to see if the model agreed with the actual experimental results. There was no significant difference between the experimental and the theoretically expected results. The null hypothesis, H₀ was satisfied.

Table 4 T –Statistic for the Controlled Points, Unwashed-Gravel Concrete Compressive Test, based on Osadebe’s Second –Degree Polynomial Polynomial

RESPONSE	i	j	a _i	a _{ij}	a _i ²	a _{ij} ²	ε	ȳ	Ŷ	t
C ₁	1	2	-0.082	0.050	0.007	0.003	0.4835	16.0	16.9	-1.58008
	1	3	-0.082	0.121	0.007	0.015				
	1	4	-0.082	0.120	0.007	0.0399				
	2	3	-0.092	0.142	0.01	0.020				
	2	4	-0.092	0.233	0.013	0.0543				
	3	4	-0.121	0.566	0.016	0.3202				
	4	—	-0.017	—	0.001	—				
			Σ	0.052	0.4316					
	Similarly									
C ₂	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.4809	16.3	15.9	0.617625
C ₃	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.9234	16.1	17.1	-1.9825
C ₄	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.4642	16.2	17.0	-1.26789
C ₅	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5053	13.5	12.8	1.086064
C ₆	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.4966	15.7	14.4	2.377246
C ₇	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5707	14.6	13.4	2.026749
C ₈	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5624	13.1	14.6	-2.72798
C ₉	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.4949	15.7	16.9	-2.20202
C ₁₀	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5236	14.8	15.3	-0.91441

LEGEND: c_i = response; a_i = z_i (2z_i - 1); a_{ij} = 4 z_i z_j; ε = Σa_i² + Σa_{ij}²; ȳ = experimentally-observed value; Ŷ = theoretical value; t = t-test statistic.

➤ *T-Value from Table*

The t-student’s test had a significance level, $\alpha = 0.05$ and $t_{\alpha/1(v_e)} = t_{0.005(9)}=3.69$. This was greater than any of the t values calculated in table 4. Therefore, the regression equation for the unwashed gravel concrete was adequate.

➤ *F-Statistic Analysis*

The sample variances S_1^2 and S_2^2 for the two sets of data were not significantly different (table 5). It implied that the error(s) from experimental procedure were similar and that the sample variances being tested are estimates of the same population variance. Based on eqn.10, we had that $S_K^2 = 12.319/9 = 1.369$, $S_E^2 = 22.486/9 = 2.498$ & $F = 1.369/2.498 = 0.548$. From Fisher’s table, $F_{0.95(9,9)} = 3.3$, hence the regression equation for the compressive strength of the unwashed gravel concrete was adequate.

Table 5 F –Statistic for the Controlled Points, Granite Concrete Compressive Strength, based on Osadebe’s Second –Degree Polynomial

Response Symbol	Y _K	Y _E	Y _K - \check{Y}_K	Y _E - \check{Y}_E	(Y _K - \check{Y}_K) ²	(Y _E - \check{Y}_E) ²
C ₁	16.0	16.9	0.778	1.450	0.606	2.102
C ₂	16.3	15.9	1.116	0.505	1.245	0.255
C ₃	16.1	17.1	0.909	1.674	0.827	2.803
C ₄	16.2	17.0	1.047	1.541	1.096	2.374
C ₅	13.5	12.8	-1.740	-2.618	3.026	6.855
C ₆	15.7	14.4	0.545	-1.085	0.297	1.178
C ₇	14.6	13.4	-0.604	-2.003	0.365	4.011
C ₈	13.1	14.6	-2.118	-0.818	4.486	0.669
C ₉	15.7	16.9	0.462	1.491	0.213	2.223
C ₁₀	14.8	15.3	-0.398	-0.122	0.158	0.015
Σ	152	154.3			12.319	22.486

Legend: $\check{Y} = \Sigma y/n$ where y is the response and n, the number of observed data (responses) y_k is the experimental value (response) y_E is the expected or theoretically calculated value (response)

IV. CONCLUSION

The strengths (responses) of concrete were a function of the proportions of its ingredients: water, cement, fine aggregate and coarse aggregates. Since the predicted strengths by the model were in total agreement with the corresponding experimentally -observed values, the null hypothesis was satisfied. This meant that the model equation was valid.

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